

AN A MDO SMYUNG GNAS: YO LAG TIBETAN COMMUNITY,
THUN RIN (REB GONG, TONGREN) CITY, MTSO SNGON
(QINGHAI) PROVINCE, PR CHINA

Pad+ma rig 'dzin བདུ་རྒྱལ་འཛིན། (Wanmarengzeng 完么仁增)*

ABSTRACT

Personal experiences, observations, preparations, daily activities, including recreational events, and interviews with locals, inform this study of a community A mdo Tibetan Smyung gnas held on the fourteenth to sixteenth days of the fourth (Chinese lunisolar calendar) in Yo lag (Zhiyue) Village, Mdo ba (Duowa) Town, Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China during the mid-twentieth to the early twenty-first centuries. Cultural preservation is served by this study, which is also a model of how local rituals might be presented at a time of rapid cultural transformation.

KEYWORDS

Mtsho sngon (Qinghai), Reb gong (Thun rin, Tongren), Sa ga zla ba, *sbyin bdag*, *sdom pa*, Smyung gnas, *thun*, Tibetan cultural preservation, Tibetan gathering, Tibetan ritual

INTRODUCTION

It was morning on the fourteenth day of the fourth lunisolar month,¹ 2016, in Yo lag (Zhiyue) Village, Mdo ba (Duowa) Town, Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.²

"Hello! Are you all ready to head out?" asked Wu ba (b. 1967), my neighbor, as she stepped inside my family house holding a string handle in her right hand that served as a bail for a stainless-steel pail full of yogurt. Her left hand clutched a small bag with a plastic container and several bowls inside.

"Yes, sit for a moment," responded my older brother's wife as she finished getting dressed.

My other family members had already gone to the Bzhi ba'i smyung gnas³ 'Fasting of the Fourth Month' (FFLM hereafter) site⁴ after we all had prostrated three times to scriptures, images of *bla ma*, and two metal images on a wooden shelf in our home that is near where we sleep and eat. We

*Pad+ma rig 'dzin (Wanmarengzeng). 2021. An A mdo Smyung gnas: Yo lag Tibetan Community, Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 60:47-73.

¹ In about 2000, several Mdo ba Town residents encouraged locals to celebrate the New Year according to the Central Tibetan calendar. Few families did so. In 2019, most of the few locals who observed the Central Tibetan New Year were monks. "Month" as used in this paper refers to the Chinese lunisolar calendar. It is also noteworthy that 'Phags pa (1235-1280), Kublai Khan's (1215-1294) tutor, introduced the system of Mongolian months to the Tibetan calendrical year (Berzin 1987:23), known as *hor zla* 'Mongol month'. Most locals born before about 1980 are illiterate, except for monks. Although locals may be unfamiliar with the historical background, they are familiar with the term *hor zla*, e.g., the twelfth Chinese lunisolar month is locally known as *hor zla bcu gnyis ba* 'the twelfth Mongol month'.

² In 2014, Mdo ba Township became Mdo ba Town and, in 2020, Thun rin (Reb gong, Thun rin) County became a city.

³ Smyung gnas locally refers to Bzhi ba'i smyung gnas and *thun* 'fasting sessions'.

⁴ Located near the center of the Ra rgan (the name of our community) winter pasture. The current FFLM location is conveniently situated by a road that runs from the town center to Rong bo Town.

did this before *sdom ja*¹ and rinsing our mouths three times after having milk tea. Brother was a *sbyin bdag* 'manager',² so he was expected to reach the FFLM site before nine AM. Sister, Father, and I went to the FFLM site in Brother's small van, and then I drove back home to pick up Sister-in-law and Wu ba.

"Sister Wu ba, are you going to give this yogurt to the managers?" asked Sister-in-law as she prepared bowls and two long carpets for my family members to sit on.

"Yes. Last year I gave some milk, but yogurt is good, so I've prepared this," Wu ba answered.

They were soon ready, so we got into the van and started off to the FFLM site.

Twenty years earlier, we had walked to the FFLM site, which had taken about thirty minutes, but now it takes only a few minutes by vehicle. We arrived at around ten AM to find most local community members already there or just arriving. The managers were busy preparing *'bras thug* 'rice cooked in butter with red dates and raisins' and *gro ma* (*Potentilla anserina* L, 'wild yams'³) for the midday meal. Some women were sitting in front of the meeting tent, chatting. Others were chanting *ma Ni*.⁴ Some male elders seated on the right side of the storage tent laughed and talked loudly. Teenagers were standing around the elders and listening. A dozen pre-school children were wandering here and there on the grassland near the tents.

My first memory of FFLM is a gathering in Yo lag in about 1997 when I was seven years old. My most recent participation was in 2016. As of early 2020, I had attended five times.

FFLM is held annually on the fourteenth, fifteenth, and sixteenth days of the fourth month. While religious fasting is central to this gathering, other activities such as food and tea preparation and entertainment activities such as tug-of-war, foot races, weight-lifting, and wrestling matches also occur. There may only be religious fasting in the case of a death in the local community or rainy weather. To better explain this gathering and its importance, it is necessary to describe certain local religious ideas and their relation to FFLM.

Locals believe that human misdeeds include physical, verbal, and mental obscuration (*lus kyi sgrib pa*, *ngag gi sgrib pa*, and *yid kyi sgrib pa*, respectively). Consequently, FFLM is practiced to diminish non-virtuous activity by not drinking, eating, and speaking. Practitioners with sincere faith may eliminate all the non-virtues they have accumulated/created in previous lives as well as present lives. This, they hope, may lead to enlightenment or incarnation in a heavenly realm.

This belief is true today due to more regular religious instruction by monks and other local religious teachers, advising people to aim for a higher goal and condemning the more mundane goals such as good health and a better rebirth. This is in contrast to the past when people mostly wished for a better human rebirth. Smyung gnas 'fasting rituals' may also be done at home, for example, on the first, fifteenth, twenty-first, and thirtieth days of each month, and for the benefit of deceased relatives and clan members. For example, my paternal cousin, Lcags thar skyid (b. 1970), often ritually fasts on auspicious days and the death anniversary of relatives.

After a death, the affected family invites monks to chant and asks local women to practice fasting. During this period, men are occupied receiving guests, cooking, and watching over the corpse at night until the time of sky burial; consequently, women are more available to engage in fasting

¹ Explained later.

² *Sbyin bdag* 'sponsors' 'patrons' 'donors' is a term for those who manage Smyung gnas. In the local context described here, the *sbyin bdag* do not use personal resources to finance the gathering. Instead, they manage it, therefore, I use the term "managers." A different English term for *sbyin bdag* may be better suited to particular local circumstances elsewhere.

³ *Gro ma* is translated variously as 'wild miniature sweet potatoes', 'wild sweet potatoes', 'wild yams', and so on. I use "wild yam."

⁴ A six-syllable mantra devoted to Avalokiteśvara, the Buddhist deity of compassion.

rituals. However, a few men, who are generally relatives of the deceased, might also participate. Typically, each family in the local community chants 10,000 *ma Ni* in the hope the deceased will be reincarnated as a human. Moreover, the deceased's family may give candy or small amounts of cash (e.g., one RMB) to children for chanting *ma Ni*. Locals chant *ma Ni* after eating food from the affected family, so children know what to do when they receive candy or money from strangers.

Furthermore, elders may tell students to chant *ma Ni*. Usually, candy and small amounts of cash are given to students when they gather on the school playground or outside the school when students go home during breaks. For example, when I attended the local primary school in 2001, a family cooked *'bras thug* for our lunch, and we chanted *ma Ni* before having this lunch. In 2019, I visited Bla brang Monastery and observed several people giving candy to pilgrims circumambulating the monastery. The pilgrims accepted the candy and began chanting *ma Ni* while eating the candy.

Why are many locals intimately and regularly involved in religious practice? As a local community member, I share my own experiences and interactions over the years with my maternal grandmother (Sgro b+ha, 1923-2010), sister (Bzung 'dus mtsho, b. 1985), sister-in-law (G.yang mo, b. 1985), and neighbor women. They are quietly confident that religious practice on sacred dates leads to an accumulation of merit. Not knowing abstract explanations for the dates' special sacredness does not minimize their belief in their importance. The women I mentioned seldom interact and exchange views with monks and other literate males who have religious ideas based on what they have read and learned in monastery-based teachings. Nevertheless, these women have sincere faith and place great value on sacred times when all positive deeds are doubled in karmic value, which they have heard repeatedly since childhood. During this time, self-restraint and austerity are believed to help attain a more positive attitude toward life and significantly contribute to a better afterlife.

The FFLM period is divided into two phases. The first - *sdom pa* 'vow of abstinence' (maintaining a pure body, mind, and speech) - is practiced on the fourteenth day, during which participants have a midday meal known as *gung tshigs*, and a milk tea break known as *sdom ja* in the morning and *rung ja* in the afternoon and evening. Fruit, candy,¹ fried bread, *rtsam pa*, yogurt, milk tea, and wild yams with ghee and rice are typical meal items. Meat, garlic, onion, and spices such as chili are not served.

The second phase is regarded as the crucial part of this period. FFLM practitioners do not speak, eat, or drink after having a tea break at dusk on the fourteenth day to the morning of the sixteenth day. Both males and females who practice *sdom pa* are locally known as *sdom pa ba* 'fasting session participants'. They decide for themselves if they are capable of participating in the fasting session. If they choose negatively, they might continue to practice *sdom pa* on the second day until the dawn of the third day. Thus, at times, the term *smyung gnas ba* loosely refers to both the fasting session and *sdom pa* practitioners.²

My community has a long history of practicing FFLM. Until about 1995, locals were mobile, tent-dwelling herders.³ Since about 1998, locals have held FFLM at a location near the center of the Ra rgan winter pasture.

In terms of attendance, all local community members participate in FFLM unless they are very weak, old, or in school. Managers are responsible for preparing and arranging a meeting tent, a kitchen tent, and a storage tent. The team consists of around twenty local men (if men are unavailable,

¹ *Ka ra* refers to various types of candy wrapped in colorful paper or plastic and also includes *ka ra rdo* 'crystal sugar'.

² On the first day of FFLM, those who will practice *thun*, could have, if they wanted, lunch and milk tea before dark (around seven PM). These practitioners do not eat or drink, nor do they speak until the early morning of the third day.

³ In 2020, a majority of locals lived in tents during the summer.

women join the managers) who take turns each year. Individual families also make cash contributions, who also provide *gro ma*, butter, dry cheese, ghee, and yogurt.

Later, I detail rituals, management, clothing, food, participants, and other activities. Local males and females of all ages are involved in this opportunity to engage in religious rituals, participate in recreational activities, and wear attractive clothing.

I now present locations used in the text, followed by relevant maps.

LOCATIONS AND MAPS

Bsang khog (Sangke) Township, Bsang chu¹ (Xiahe) County, Kan lho (Gannan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Kan su'u (Gansu) Province

Mkha' skya (Kashijia) Village, a small herding community of Mdo ba Town

Ra rgya (Lajia) a township in Rma chen (Maqin) County, Mgo log (Guoluo) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon Province

Yo lag (Zhiyue) Village, the official name for a small herding community in Mdo ba Town. It is also a local term for residents of Ra rgan, Rin kho, and 'Ja' mo ru khag 'dui' 'brigades' 'small local communities'.

FIG 1. Mtsho sngon Province.²

¹ Locally known as Bla brang.

² Edited versions of <https://bit.ly/2LzoTSG> (accessed 6 July 2019).

FIG 2. Thun rin City.¹

¹ Edited version of <https://bit.ly/2xyGmCE> (accessed 6 July 2019).

² An edited version of <https://bit.ly/2MY4eXo> (accessed 20 October 2019). Families typically had a winter pasture (ninth to sixth months) and a summer pasture (seventh to eighth months). Certain families also rented pastures for about one month where they herded livestock and afterward, went to their own winter pasture in the tenth month. These times were approximate.

YO LAG VILLAGE - OFFICIAL AND UNOFFICIAL

The officially designated Yo lag Village is a herding community in Mdo ba Town. In 2010, it had about 253 families and 1,119 residents.¹ Officially, Yo lag is home to the seven brigades listed below:

'Ja' mo	Bla brang ma	Blon che	Bon po
Dpon skor	Ra rgan	Rin kho	

Before 1958, Yo lag designated Ra rgan, Rin kho, and 'Ja' mo brigades. In 2018, these three brigades had about ninety families (300 people). Locals continue to use this designation today. However, in about 1958, the government created the following administrative divisions:

- 'Ja' mo → Tos bzhi ba (Sidui) 'Brigade Number Four'
- Bla brang ma → Tos gsum pa (Sandui) 'Brigade Number Three'
- Blon che → Tos drug pa (Liudui) 'Brigade Number Six'
- Bon po → Tos gnyis ba (Erdui) 'Brigade Number Two'
- Dbon skor → Tos bdun pa (Qidui) 'Brigade Number Seven'
- Ra rgan → Tos dang po (Yidui) 'Brigade Number One'
- Rin kho → Tos lnga ba (Wudui) 'Brigade Number Five'

These seven brigades collectively comprise the officially designated Yo lag Village whose residents follow the Dge lugs School and hold religious activities in the local monastery, Mdo sngags dar rgyas gling located on a hill, southwest of Grong brdal thog.²

A majority of adult residents are illiterate. However, from around 1998, the enrolment of children in the local primary school located in Grong brdal thog increased, coinciding with the implementation of the Nine-Year Compulsory Education policy and parents' realization there was a direct relationship between schooling and social mobility.³ After graduation, a majority of the students attend middle schools in Rong bo (Longwu) Town. Boys who do not continue their education become monks, herders, or find employment outside their home (described later). Girls usually marry and become housewives or find work elsewhere.

Traditionally, all community members were herders, except for monks. Those who live in Grong brdal thog are locally called Mtha' ba 'outskirt residents'. Later, with the implementation of the Meili xiangcun jianshe 'Construction of the Beautiful Countryside' policy,⁴ the number of people leaving Yo lag to live at least part-time in Grong brdal thog increased. From 2015 to the present, the government subsidized and built 240 houses for villagers. In 2018, almost every Yo lag family had a house in Grong brdal thog.

The project relocating families to Grong brdal thog was known as Yidi fupin banqian 'Relocating the Poor'⁵ that was part of China's thirteenth five-year plan for economic and social development targeting poverty elimination and constructing a comprehensive well-off society in five years. Mdo ba leaders began implementing this policy in 2018.

During a meeting I attended on 13 September 2018, town and village leaders announced that families were required to put furniture in their new houses to appear to be living there. Failure to

¹ The 2018 population data here and below were provided by village leaders in August 2018.

² This is the local term for the Mdo ba Town center. For a video of this location made in 2019, see <https://bit.ly/2KBllP3> (accessed 14 August 2010).

³ China's education policy requires all school-aged children to receive education for a minimum of nine years.

⁴ See Gonier and Rgyal yum sgröl ma (2012) for more on resettlement policies.

⁵ <https://bit.ly/2PsjKMc> (accessed 22 April 2019).

comply, the leaders stated, could result in confiscation of the house that had been provided, which might be given to another family.

In 2015, resettled locals worked at construction sites in Grong brdal thog, and were paid about 120 RMB per day. In 2018, the building that was part of Construction of the Beautiful Countryside ended, resulting in many fewer construction jobs. Additionally, many laborers were available from outside the township, including Tibetans from farming areas and Chinese. Finding employment in Grong brdal thog became very difficult for resettled locals.

In the autumn of 2018, about six men and three women originally from Yo lag Village moved to urban areas such as Chongqing, Guangdong, and Guangzhou to work in response to advertisements on WeChat translated into Tibetan. The ads sought to recruit cheap labor from rural Tibetan areas for jobs welding and assembling and pasting labels on computer shells.¹

Some young villagers told me that working for a large company was not very difficult, and the payment was acceptable. However, some elders voiced disappointment, commenting that the middleman who introduced locals to the company was dishonest, e.g., if the company paid seventeen RMB per hour, the middleman paid the laborers only thirteen RMB per hour. Unfortunately, some villagers signed a contract with the middleman and did not receive payment directly from the company. These employees complained that the labor was difficult and worried that the middleman might not pay them promptly.

In the following sections, I examine Bzhi ba'i smyung gnas, preparation, the first day, the second day, the third day, and recreational/entertainment activities; and present and analyze interviews with villagers that provide a local historical context for FFLM.

FASTING OF THE FOURTH MONTH

The first day of Smyung gnas is the practice of *sdom pa*, the preliminary part of the ritual, before *thun* 'the more ascetic or intensification of the *sdom pa* vow by remaining silent, not drinking and eating' on the second day, which continues until the dawn of the third day. Sa ga zla ba² is a term indicating the fourth month. Sa ga zla ba'i dus chen refers to the gathering.

Locals and scholars such as Dkon mchog bstan pa'i sgron me³ (nd) and Blo bzang bstan dar (1994) write that the ritual system for Smyung gnas originated with Dge slong ma dpal mo. Vargas-O'bryan (2001) identifies her as Bhiksuni Lakssmi, who most likely lived during the tenth to eleventh centuries. Blo bzang bstan dar (1994) notes that Dge slong ma dpal mo was born as a princess of Indian King Indrabhūti and Queen Yid 'ong bzang mo on the fifteenth day of the first month. Similarly, a local elder, Lha mo skyabs (b. 1958), narrated:

If monk scholars or a *bla ma* were invited to Smyung gnas, they gave a sermon on Smyung gnas transmission, instruction, virtues, and achievements of the Smyung gnas founder, Dge slong ma dpal mo. She suffered from leprosy, but in practicing Smyung gnas, she completely recovered.

A paragraph of Dge slong ma dpal mo's hagiography follows:

¹ From interviews, I learned that a Chinese man (a go-between) had paid a Tibetan acquaintance to translate an ad into Tibetan and post the translation in his WeChat groups that have many Tibetan subscribers. The go-between would then keep part of what the company paid to a worker recruited in this way. A second method is for a Tibetan worker at a company to recruit workers from his home area and subsequently receive compensation. Local labor migration in the Reb gong area deserves more study. There may be other ways of communication involved. Some local reports suggest that a family member or friend already working in an urban area encourages locals to follow their example.

² Illiterate locals born before about 1980 might be unfamiliar with the term "Sa ga zla ba."

³ For biographical details, see <https://bit.ly/2JI9oVS> (accessed 16 July 2019).

After she had been staying in the vicinity of the eleven-faced and practicing *smyung gnas*, she vowed not to go anywhere else until she had achieved the supreme attainment in that place. So, not thinking about food or drink, day and night she continuously performed the *sādhana* of the eleven-faced. After a year had passed, her bodily illness had completely disappeared like a snake shedding its skin (Sangseraima Ujeed 2016:138).

Ritual implications, virtue, and the meaning of *Smyung gnas* have been dealt with elsewhere (Dkon mchog sbtan pa'i sgron me, nd:160-189), including how it helps in the afterlife and how it assists practitioners to have notable life achievements such as visualizing eleven manifestations of Avalokitesvara, which is an indicator of diligent practice.

In 2019, online searches for "*Smyung gnas*" and "*Sa ga zla ba*" produced few results in Tibetan, Chinese, and English. Vargas-O'bryan (2001), Sangseraima Ujeed (2016), and a hagiography (Blo bzang bstan dar 1994) of *Dge slong ma dpal mo* were consulted; however, little information relates to ritual gatherings.

Dkon mchog bstan pa'i sgron me (nd:160-189) explains the principles and religious merits of practicing *Smyung gnas* in the context of Buddhist theology as it applies to ordinary people. Tshen brtan (1993), 'Brug mo thar (2014), and Sang rgyas skyabs (2018) describe *Smyung gnas* in the *Bsang chu* area, including explanations for principles of practice and daily activities during the *Smyung gnas* period. Sang rgyas skyabs (2018) provides the origins of *Smyung gnas* and gives a short life history of *Dge slong ma dpal mo*, emphasizing the virtue of practicing *Smyung gnas* and explaining the implications of *Smyung gnas* customs in the Buddhist context, as well as the local practical benefits of *Smyung gnas* based on *Bsang khog Township*, which he identifies as strengthening a sense of community and also having health benefits.¹

Sang rgyas skyabs (2018) observed changes in this ritual in *Bsang khog*, and how it compares to Ramadan through interviews with Muslims² living in *Bsang khog*.

Yu Shiyu, a Chinese Tibetologist, sketches (1941:359-362) general activities of ritual days, expenses, and other details two days before the ritual when women combed their hair and plaited small braids with the help of three women, and wore elaborate clothing and expensive jewelry. Female practitioners outnumbered the male practitioners. Of the upper and lower *Mtha' ba* 'outskirt residents' in *Bsang chu* (Xiahe) County Town, the former comprised 300 families. Twenty-five families annually alternated, making preparations for the ritual each year. The lower *Mtha' ba* had about one hundred families. Each year eleven families took turns managing the ritual. During the midday meal, all practitioners gathered at the public hall to eat.

Lcags mo 'tsho describes the *Smyung gnas* of *Reb gong Bon* followers³ and mentions *Bzhi ba'i smyung gnas* but does not describe it. Details for the practice of *Smyung gnas* in the context of *Bon* scripture, and time and location of observing a collective *Smyung gnas* practice, as well as religious implications and *Smyung gnas* taboos are provided.⁴

¹ It is locally thought that very old people and ill people should not abstain from eating and drinking for a prolonged period, but that such practice does not harm younger, healthy people.

² They lived in *Bsang khog* for several decades (Sang rgyas skyabs 2018:35).

³ Sang rgyas skyabs (2018) indicated this paper was written in 2008. I located it on <https://bit.ly/2YxIs1u> (accessed 1 July 2019).

⁴ Yang Xianhui's (2009) short story "*Niangnai jie*," based on *Smyung gnas* in the *Kan lho* area, misrepresents *Smyung gnas* activity.

BZHI BA'I SMYUNG GNAS

Sa ga zla ba is a term for the fourth month, which locals consider the date Siddhārtha Gautama entered the womb, was enlightened, and died. Sangs rgyas skyabs (2018:09) points out six auspicious days per month to practice Smyung gnas. Religious virtues accrued on the significantly auspicious fifteenth day of Sa ga zla ba are magnified. Consequently, Tibetans often cultivate virtue and shun wrong deeds by practicing *Smyung gnas*. As Cabezón notes:

The fourth Tibetan month, called Sagadawa (*sa ga zla ba*), is arguably the holiest month of the Buddhist liturgical year, the month in which Tibetans celebrate the Buddha's birth, and according to some sources, also his enlightenment and death. Sagadawa is a particularly popular time for engaging in communal fasting rites known as *nyungné* (*Smyung gnas*) (2010:02).

Historically, there was no fixed location for FFLM. However, since about 2012, locals have observed FFLM in the same general location, which is four kilometers from Grong brdal thog as already described. Therefore, it is convenient for villagers in terms of transportation, although it is not the entire community's exact geographical center.

On the first day of FFLM, local ritual participants have only a midday meal and *rung ja*. Those observing this schedule are known as *sdom pa ba*. *Thun* is observed after a final consumption of tea and food on the evening of the second day, followed by not talking, eating, or drinking until the dawn of the third day. However, practitioners may continue to be *sdom pa* if they so choose.

At daybreak on the third and final day of FFLM, *thun* ends with a meal of *thor thug* 'milk boiled with dried cheese and wheat flour'. After a communal lunch, attendees return home. Certain locals do not eat meat for the entire fourth month.

Residents of the official Yo lag Village do not observe FFLM together. Instead, each community has a particular location for FFLM. For example, residents of Bon po, Blon che, and Bla brang ma (collectively known as 'Gro skor by locals),¹ observe FFLM together near Grong brdal thog. Dbon skor is an independent community and holds FFLM in the center of their winter pasture.

FFLM PREPARATION

FFLM preparation begins on the twelfth day of the fourth month. The *sbyin bdag*² are responsible for FFLM from beginning to end, collecting *rus cha* 'contributions' from villagers; and pitching a large *tshogs ras* 'meeting/assembly tent', a *ja ras* 'kitchen tent', and a small tent for storing food. They also cook lunch for the *sdom pa ba*, who only have lunch and milk tea in the morning and afternoon. The managers neither practice *sdom pa* nor *thun* in recognition of the many tasks they must perform. Yo lag families are divided into two groups.³ In 2018, one group had forty-six members, and the other had fifty-five. These groups assumed responsibility for FFLM activities in alternating years. The

¹ 'Gro skor is a local term for residents of Bon po, Blon che, and Bla brang ma brigades who collectively participate in Smyung gnas.

² Sang rgyas skyabs (2018:15) mentions *sbyin bdag* in Bsang khog Township and gives the daily cost for attendees during the Smyung gnas period.

³ During Smyung gnas in 2019, elders announced that all traditional Yo lag families must participate in Smyung gnas and further, that the names of those absent would be announced. The managers were divided into four groups. Two groups each had twenty-three members, one group had twenty-eight, and another had twenty-seven members. The four groups were to take turns being managers. Rnam lo (b. 1991) provided this information via WeChat 25 June 2019 on images of four pages of handwritten notebook paper. At the top of one paper appeared the date: the sixteenth day of the fourth month 2019.

managers bring the meeting tent, pots, and the large metal stove stored in their homes and pitch the three tents at the same location as in previous years.

Beginning on the thirteenth day of the fourth month, families take contributions to the FFLM location. The managers write the names of those who gave contributions (wild yams, butter, and dry cheese) in a notebook.

In about 2013, *rtsam pa* was collected. However, at present (2019), the managers buy *rtsam pa* from Grong brdal thog shops. Contributions are collected according to *sa skal* 'land allotment' - the land assigned to a single individual. Food is collected according to the land size of a family's winter pasture and cash according to a family's summer pasture size.

Skal 'portion' refers to a certain amount of food given to each practitioner at the midday meal each day of this period and is described later in more detail. Ritual practitioners are both male and female. The youngest participants are generally around sixteen-years-old.

Contributions and *skal* are now described based on FFLM in 2018. Two families' contributions are given in FIG 4.

FIG 4. FFLM contributions (2018).

		Family Leader's Name	
		Chos kho	Tshe 'phags
land allotment	summer pasture	5 people	5 people
	winter pasture	6 people	5 people
<i>rus cha</i>	butter (0.4 kg/person)	2.4 kg	2.0 kg
	cheese (0.5 kg/person)	3.0 kg	2.5 kg
	wild yams (1 bowl/ person)	6 Tibetan bowls	5 Tibetan bowls
	cash	200 RMB	200 RMB
<i>smyung gnas ba</i>		4 people	3 people
<i>skal</i>	wild yams (1 bowl/ person)	4 Tibetan bowls	3 Tibetan bowls
	<i>mar khu</i> 'ghee' (1 ladle/person)	4 ladles	3 ladles
	bread (3/person)	12	9
	sugar (1 bowl/person)	4 Tibetan bowls	3 Tibetan bowls

FIG 5. Tibetan bowl. Local shop owners purchase bowls from Ka chu (Linxia, Gansu Province) and sell them in Grong brdal thog. The bowl in this photo is referred to as *tshe ring lo brgya* 'long life' and features conch shell patterns considered auspicious and suggestive of a life of one hundred years (2019, Pad+ma rig 'dzin's home, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

The managers must be present during preparation days unless there is an urgent reason to be absent, e.g., serious illness. Otherwise, a fine of fifty RMB per day is charged.

Older managers purchase *rtsam pa*, bread, sugar, and other foods based on their experience. They heat ghee, boil wild yams, and cook '*bras thug* using their previous experience to

determine amounts of the ingredients and cooking time. For example, the proportion of butter and sugar in the rice affects its taste. It might be too oily and/or too sweet. Heating butter and ghee is also challenging. Excessive heat might ignite the liquid ghee when heating butter to make ghee, but the butter does not separate into solids and ghee if the heat is too low. FIG 6 describes the process of cooking rice, making ghee, and boiling wild yams.

FIG 6. Cooking rice, making ghee, and boiling wild yams.

Food	Process
'bras thug	(1) Wash the rice; (2) heat a pot, smear butter inside the pot to prevent the rice from burning, and add water; (3) heat water, add rice, sugar, raisins, and jujubes, and gradually reduce the heat after the mixture begins boiling to avoid burning.
butter	(1) Heat a thick pot and add butter; (2) use electric bellows and when the butter melts, stir with a stick when the butter boils; (3) it is <i>btsags thag chod pa</i> 'purified completely' when large bubbles are gone. Reduce the heat. If tiny bubbles appear, the butter is burning. A drop of ghee is dropped into the fire. It is a good sign if only smoke is given off. If the sound " <i>tsag tsag</i> " is heard, the ghee should boil longer.
wild yams	The wild yams are boiled. If there is a large quantity, it is removed from the pot, put on a piece of plastic, and carried to a river. Water is dipped with a basin from the river and poured on the wild yams to cool them; otherwise, gray liquid forms on the wild yams, which is locally termed <i>tsha langs ba</i> 'got a fever', and the color and taste are negatively affected.

On the thirteenth day of the fourth month, the managers have usually completed preparations. *Su ru* 'dry rhododendron' for kindling and *ong ba* 'dried yak dung' were historically prepared. However, in the early twenty-first century, coal was purchased, replacing yak dung as fuel. Previously, the managers' wives made an adobe stove that accommodated two or three pots. However, once coal was available beginning in about 2008, a large metal stove was purchased. A coal-fired flame produced more heat than a dung-fueled fire.

FIG 7. In summer and autumn, local women collect rhododendron, which is dried and used to start a fire. In about 2014, the local Forestry Bureau announced that cutting rhododendron was forbidden. However, collecting continues in remote pasture areas (summer pasture, Yo log; 2019, Sha bo don grub).

FIG 8. The large metal stove, butter lamps, pots, and bags of coal in the kitchen tent (2016, Yo lag, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Managers' families provide milk. Some locals voluntarily contribute milk, which is used to make milk tea and yogurt for the ritual practitioners. In the early twenty-first century, milk was used to make *yar tshogs thug pa*, which is similar to but much thicker than *thor thug*. This was done on the evening of the thirteenth day for those who would later practice *sdom pa* or *thun*. Traditionally, certain managers shouted, "*Ki! Yar tshogs thug pa 'thung gi shog!* 'Hey! Everyone come eat *yar tshogs thug pa!*'"

Before about the year 2000, transportation was inconvenient, e.g., there were no motorcycles. At that time and earlier, attendees came to FFLM on the thirteenth day of the fourth month and pitched tents around the meeting tent. Locals' memories of FFLM in their childhood suggest that it was very different from the contemporary gathering. For example, Tshe brtan (b. 1970) said that families far from the FFLM site drove their livestock to FFLM. Furthermore, before about 1980, there was no private grassland. This changed in the 1990s when the land was twice divided among locals. In about 1997, I recall families far from the FFLM site arriving early and pitching tents for elders and children. Meanwhile, young couples went to and from their homes on horseback to tend their livestock in the mornings and evenings.

Motorcycles and cars were in everyday use in about 2005. Therefore, no private tents were pitched near the meeting tent. Today, if someone must spend the night at or near the gathering site and cannot easily return home, families near the FFLM site provide a room.

In about 2007, the managers no longer shouted for people to come because nobody attended. The ritual participants did not spend the night at the FFLM site because that required a tent, blankets, and sheets. It was considered more convenient to go home by car or motorcycle. Moreover, FFLM falls during the time caterpillar fungus (*Ophiocordyceps sinensis*) is collected. At this time, many local ritual participants camp in distant mountains for days. Consequently, female ritual participants who collected caterpillar fungus in the winter pastures had many chores at their homes when they returned such as collecting, piling up, and carrying dry yak dung to their home for use as fuel. Once male ritual participants who collected caterpillar fungus returned home, they fed ill and weak lambs and purchased supplies for the area where they were camping.

THE FIRST DAY

On the fourteenth day of the fourth month participants drink milk tea around eight AM, eat a meal at noon, and have milk tea again at seven PM. This practice is locally known as *sdom pa*. Certain taboos are observed before engaging in *sdom pa*. Practitioners must be *gtsang ma* 'clean' from the fourteenth to sixteenth days, which requires avoiding alcohol and *dmar* 'meat'. Furthermore, practitioners do not drink or eat from unwashed containers to ensure that they are unpolluted. Sexual intercourse during this period for those observing *sdom pa* is also taboo. Garlic and onions are usually not eaten in the seven days before FFLM.

Before eight AM, practitioners wash their face and hands, remove their shoes, and do three prostrations. This is known as *bskums phyag*.¹ From about eight AM, *sdom pa ba* have *sdom ja*. Practitioners sit comfortably before drinking milk tea, and if they like, eat candy. There are no limits on time or the amount of tea to drink. However, practitioners should not move or stand before rinsing their mouths three times with water known as *chab* 'water used in a ritual context' that the managers pour into one of their palms. The practitioners sip the *chab* in their palm, rinse their mouths, and spit it on the ground. Participants do this three times and may then move and stand up as they like. Next, participants should not eat or drink until the midday meal. During FFLM, most locals wear Tibetan robes.

After *sdom ja* at about nine AM, locals begin gathering for FFLM, wearing their *phyor l+wa* 'fancy clothes' if nobody has passed away in the community. *Rgya zhwa* 'Tibetan felt hat', coral necklaces, gold necklaces, *ras l+wa* 'textile robes', high-heeled leather shoes, belts featuring silver panels inlaid with coral, and coral-pendant-gold earrings are considered ideal traditional adornments for young women. New, fashionable shirts and pants are also popular attire worn under *ras l+wa*.

Young men commonly wear *phrug l+wa* 'red woolen robes', leather boots, and gold necklaces. A majority wear *ras l+wa*, sports or leather shoes, and new shirts and pants.

The managers busily prepare the midday meal, milk tea, and *bras thug*; melt butter; and boil wild yams for the ritual practitioners in the morning to ensure that they are well prepared before noon.

At about eleven-thirty AM, the ritual practitioners prepare to eat a midday meal. They first wash their hands, and bowls and other containers that are used during lunch. The practitioners prostrate three times to the *mchod khri* 'altar' in the upper-middle section of the meeting tent where butter lamps and Buddha and high bla ma images are placed. Afterward, they sit in lines on carpets brought from their homes. Local monks or *bla ma* are sometimes invited to chant in front of the altar.

¹ Locally, a form of prostration, *bskums phyag* involves touching one's knees, elbows, and forehead to the ground. In contrast, *brkyangs phyag* is a full-body prostration.

FIG 9. The three FFLM tents (2016, Yo lag, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

FIG 10. The new meeting tent and two other tents (Yo lag, 2019, 'Brug dkar tshe ring).

During the midday meal, the managers ask participating families, "*Khyed tshang la smyung gnas ba du yod* 'How many practitioners does your family have?'"

The reply determines how many portions are given. Fruit, ghee, bread, and white sugar are provided according to the number of ritual practitioners a family has. A family without ritual practitioners does not receive a share, but they are expected to contribute *rus cha* to the managers. Though no one is punished, there is a general willingness to contribute because it is believed to be a way to acquire merit. *Rtsam pa*, dry cheese, and butter are placed in small plastic bags along the lines of ritual practitioners seated on carpets.

FIG 11. Ritual practitioners have a midday meal in the meeting tent (2016, Yo lag, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Ritual practitioners eat as much as they like during the midday meal. Once satisfied, they make three *changs bu*¹ to which they add bits of each food they had for *gung tshigs*. The managers bring water in teapots and offer it to the ritual practitioners as described earlier. After the participants rinse their mouths three times, they stand and move about as usual. They take their *changs bu* outside the meeting tent and put them where they will not be stepped on. Ritual practitioners take leftover food to their homes except for *rtsam pa*, dry cheese, and butter. Previously, practitioners mixed wild yams and ghee with *rtsam pa*, creating a small ball locally known as *rtsam pa sgor log/gro log 'gro ma ball*', which was convenient to take home. In 2016, each food offered by the managers was placed in containers, e.g., wild yams and ghee were put in different containers.

Next, it is lunchtime for children, who sit outside the meeting tent in a circle. The managers offer them the various foods they have prepared. *'Bras thug*, milk tea, fruit, and bread are placed in the center of the children. Nowadays, however, few children attend FFLM because they are in school. Afterward, it is lunchtime for the managers, who sit in a circle outside if it is sunny. Otherwise, they sit in the kitchen tent and meeting tent to enjoy the food. Finally, young managers serve food to the elders.

¹ This is done by making *rtsam pa* without cheese in a bowl, gripping it tightly in the hand, and using the thumb to press down on the top of the *rtsam pa*. The other four fingers make prints on the *rtsam pa*, putting a small ball of *rtsam pa* in the ring finger indentation, and adding small bits of each food in plastic plates for *gung tshigs*. Three *changs bu* of similar size are made after *gung tshigs*.

FIG 12. Pre-schoolers have 'bras thug and yogurt for lunch (2016, Yo lag, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

FIG 13. The managers have lunch (2016, Yo lag, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Locals return home at around five PM. In the past, many participants stayed and slept in the meeting tent. However, in 2016, only the managers stayed overnight to protect food from dogs and the tents from damage by livestock and strong wind. After returning home at about eight PM, the practitioners have *rung ja*, the same as the morning milk tea break. First, they drink milk tea and eat

candy. Next, they rinse their mouths with water three times and prostrate before having *rung ja*.¹ The ritual practitioners may move their upper torsos but are expected not to move their buttocks during tea time. They do not eat dinner, and they go to bed early.

THE SECOND DAY

The fifteenth day of the fourth month is *thun*. Ritual practitioners do not speak, eat, and drink until the dawn of the third day. Those unable to practice *thun* may choose to be *sdom pa* on the second day of FFLM. According to Gcod le (b. 1937), all ritual practitioners had to be *thun* during the second day until a monk of Dar zhing Monastery² permitted locals to continue *sdom pa* on the second day without the intensified form of *thun*. Later, increasing numbers of villagers were *sdom pa* during the second day of FFLM. He added it was embarrassing that, other than a few older women who were *thun*, many young people were *sdom pa* during the second day of FFLM in 2018. He felt that it would be better to be *thun* on this special day, especially for young males and females.

Practitioners who are *thun* generally abstain from all food and drinks (including water); however, if some cannot bear discomfort from hunger and thirst, they break the *thun* rules and have yogurt known as *dkar cog* at mid-day.³ However, they must continue not to speak.

THE THIRD DAY

In the past, at dawn on the sixteenth day of the fourth month, the managers shouted, "*Ki thor thug 'thung gi shog!* 'Hey everybody! Come eat *thor thug!*" announcing a soup made of wheat flour, a little cheese, and milk.

Before about 2003, most of those in the meeting tent at night and neighbor families assembled to eat *thor thug*. It was thus necessary to cook *thor thug* for the *smyung gnas ba*. After the managers shouted, the ritual practitioners began to get up and wash their faces, hands, and bowls; prostrate three times; and sit in lines.

The managers bring *thor thug* in small metal basins to the *smyung gnas ba*, who sip the *thor thug*, rinse their mouths three times, and begin eating the *thor thug*. While eating *thor thug*, the practitioners are not allowed to eat such solid food as bread. *Thor thug* is a soup composed of the same ingredients as *yar tshogs thug pa* but with more liquid. After having *thor thug*, the ritual practitioners were expected to stay awake and not eat until sunrise.

In the morning, people greet participants who practiced *thun* with "*Smyung gnas e bde tha!* 'How is your *thun* going?'"

The reply is very positive if there have been no problems with the practice, for example, too hungry to sleep at night, extreme thirst, and sleepiness during the daytime.⁴ *Sdom pa* practitioners

¹ In Sgro b+ha's time, in the absence of timepieces, attendees observed their palms at dusk. If palm lines were not visible, it was time for *rung ja*.

² Located on a mountain about three kilometers south of Chu khog (Qukuhu) Township Town, it was constructed around 1938 (Nian and Bai 1993:167). In 2013, because of a landslide and warnings that the hill would continue to slide, the monastery was moved two kilometers southeast of Chu khog Township Town. In 2019, the monastery had around fifty monks (based on information I received from a resident monk (Tshul khriims bstan 'dzin, b. 1994), via WeChat on 11 June 2019).

³ When I was about twelve-years-old (~2002), Bzung 'dus mtshol practiced *thun*, and our grandmother allowed her to have *dkar cog*. *Dkar* 'white' may refer to yogurt. *Cog* probably derives from *gcog* 'discount', so the combination of the two terms suggests 'reduce hunger by eating yogurt'.

⁴ Locals believe ritual practitioners should not sleep during the daytime.

were not greeted in this way because *sdom pa* practice was considered easier than *thun*.¹

During *gung tshigs*, ritual practitioners are given *skal* on the first day of FFLM. The midday meal is followed by tea time for those who will be managers the following year. All the managers for the next gathering sit in two lines or a circle in the meeting tent. The current managers hospitably offer food. These two different groups of managers tease each other and make the audience laugh. In the past, some future managers teased the current managers very humorously, e.g., "Your food is bad." "You didn't offer as much food to the ritual practitioners as we did last year." "Where is your ghee? We haven't seen it."

In response, the current managers forced them to drink ghee or poured a bowl of liquid ghee on their heads, which was not done in 2019.

The main foods at this time are ghee, wild yams, and yogurt. A bowl of yogurt with a topping of wild yams for each person who will be managers the following year is offered. Historically, they teased managers, and a ladle of yogurt was poured on their heads. Locals considered this auspicious, so a little yogurt was poured on the heads of the following year's managers. Elders said that such teasing as pouring yogurt and ghee on the head and forcing people to overeat were once common, but is rare today. For example, yogurt was poured on the head of all the following year's managers in the past. However, in 2016, very few people had yogurt poured on their heads.

FIG 14. Yogurt on the head (2016, Yo lag, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Next, it is time to distribute the meeting tent, poles, metal stove, kitchen tent, and the *mdzod ras* 'storage tent' to the following year's managers. Names are written on pieces of paper and chosen randomly from a hat. Those selected carefully keep these public items until the next year when they bring them to the FFLM site and prepare.

¹ A personal experience of practicing *thun* in Dkar mdzes¹ in about 1998 illustrates difficulties: "...Mother and Aunt looked at me occasionally but said nothing. They were afraid I would forget and speak. My stomach was churning. My throat was very dry, and I was breathless" (Sonam 2011:94).

ACTIVITIES DURING FFLM

Activities are arranged on the first day of FFLM after *gung tshigs* and on the morning of the last day. During the second day of FFLM, the majority of ritual participants were *thun* participants, so a great deal of physical activity was difficult. Physical activities while serving as *thun* increase the level of hunger.

Activities such as foot races, singing, wrestling, tug-of-war, and back hip rotations¹ on a horizontal pole do not follow a fixed schedule. If a community member passes away, or there are few attendees, such activities are not held for a year.

A large ceremony is held when the number of FFLM (a *sdom pa* and a *thun* are counted as one) reaches 1,000. Locals invite a *bla ma* to FFLM and solemnly celebrate. According to Lha mo skyabs (b. 1958), a local elder, Stong skor ston mo 'Celebration of One Thousand' was held in the past. A *bla ma* was invited to conduct Thugs rje chen po'i sbyin sbreg 'Burnt-offering for the Great Compassionate' during the celebration.

The races have two sections based on age. One section is for children divided by, for example, five-to-nine and ten-to-sixteen. The second section is the seventeen-and-older group and might include runners forty-or-older if they would like to compete.² The top five runners in the second section are awarded cash or such items as towels. The second group champion receives about 200 RMB in cash or other items; for example, the first-place finisher in 2007 won a cellphone with a cash value of about 500 RMB. Children are awarded candy or a small amount of cash.

The *thag 'then* 'tug-of-war'³ is often between the current managers and the future ones. Both groups have an equal number of people. If there are many people, one group is divided into two teams in the same group. Women participate in this activity in women's teams and are divided, as are the men. The two female groups are made up of wives or members of current or future managers' families. Each winning team member receives a thermos, towel, or bag of washing powder.

Elders are fond of singing activities during FFLM. Locals sit in a circle while the singer stands in the center and performs traditional songs. The audience asks those who sing well to perform, although anyone may volunteer to sing. Singers are given gifts, e.g., a new *ska rags* 'sash' or *ling* 'strip of expensive silk'.

G.yug res or *'ju res* 'wrestling' measures two people's strength by holding each other's sashes and trying to make the competitor fall. Both can be males or females. This was popular before the mid-1980s. In the past, if two men or boys met in the mountains while herding, they might have wrestled to see who was stronger. During FFLM, young males who thought they were physically strong might have visited another village's FFLM to wrestle. The winner received no award but became well-known among locals. In 2019, locals wrestled but did not visit other FFLM to wrestle.

Another activity - *'gyogs rdo* or *sa sgye* - is lifting one hundred kilograms of earth in a bag and putting it on the shoulder or holding it in front of the chest. Contestants walk as far as they can. The person who covers the longest distance⁴ is declared the winner, receives a small gift of about fifty RMB, and is known as the strongest community member. A man of great strength might toss a bag

¹ Locally known as *ka thog nas 'khor*.

² The divisions of these groups are flexible, for example, if someone is fifteen, tall, and strong, he might join the second section.

³ Lha mo skyabs (b. 1958), a local villager, told me that hemp ropes were used in competition in his childhood. He had heard that leather ropes had been used before his time, suggesting a long local history of tug-of-war.

⁴ The longest distance might be about twenty meters.

full of earth over his head or one of his shoulders without touching his body.¹ Generally, a man can only put the heavy bag on his shoulder and let it fall off.

In the past, locals made back hip rotations on a pole. Several people held the pole ends on their shoulders. I saw a man make back hip rotations on a pole dozens of times without a pause in my childhood. Nowadays, people no longer do this.

In the end, managers scatter candies among the crowd, which locals scramble to collect. Leftover food is sold for a low price to whoever wants it. For example, if several people want a bag of cheese or *rtsam pa*, their names might be written on pieces of paper, which are put in a hat. After stirring the folded papers in a hat with their hand, someone randomly chooses a paper, opens it, and shows the name of the person who may buy the item. Managers next collect rubbish, which will be piled and burned near the FFLM site. Locals gradually leave.

INTERVIEWS WITH VILLAGERS

I interviewed young people and elders via WeChat. I also met the oldest men in our local community - Gcod le (b. 1937) and Tshe bkra (b. 1946) - in Gcod le's home. I also consulted Khon thar (b. 1970) in his home in Grong brdal thog. Elders provided information about FFLM in the past, including accounts of teasing each other during FFLM. I now focus on FFLM in the past and how people gathered during the Great Leap Forward (1958-1961) and the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976).

ACCOUNT ONE: GCOD LE

The first FFLM I remember, was held on the fourteenth to sixteenth days of the fifth month. The meeting tent was borrowed from 'Gro skor. We couldn't hold it on time, because those were very difficult times. In that year, Mdo ba'i dpon po 'the great leader of Mdo ba' was killed by A mchog [Amuquhu]² during a conflict over livestock stealing [~1947].³

Our meeting tent was taken to Dar zhing Monastery for safekeeping but was burned when Rgya mA jag tshang 'Ma Bufang's army'⁴ attacked.

At that time, 'Gro skor kept their meeting tent, so it was fine during those hard times. I was really fond of the meeting tent's lining with its colorful designs.

We continued to hold FFLM in the following years until about 1958. We didn't have a meeting tent, so we put up a *ras gur klad nag* 'tent with a *re lde* "black yak-hair cloth" top' and a *ras gur dkar mdong* 'small white fabric tent'. We had a small number of residents at that time, so the two tents collectively provided enough space to accommodate all the traditional Yo lag Village residents. Three pillars supported an interior horizontal wooden pole.

¹ Ordinary men may raise a heavy bag easily, prop it up with bent knees, continue to raise the bag, hold it against their chest, and finally slowly position it on one of their shoulders from which the bag falls off.

² A herding township in Kan lho Prefecture.

³ Gcod le dates this event with, "Tshe bkra was a baby and his father often carried him on his back."

⁴ Ma Bufang (1903-1975) was governor of Mtsho sngon Province from 1938-1949 (<https://bit.ly/32ISK1am> (accessed 21 July 2019). Local elders referred to Ma's Army as Rgya mA chi tshang because Ma Bufang's father was Ma Qi (1869-1931).

We couldn't hold Smung gnas during the hard times for a while, but policies relaxed in about 1962. Locals then held FFLM, horse races, and Chos thog.¹ I was released from prison in 1963.² Policies tightened again, and locals who had managed the religious activities in 1962 were criticized, so we didn't hold FFLM for a long time.

We couldn't afford a meeting tent until the government hired some of our pack yaks to deliver bags of flour from Reb gong to Ra rgya (Lajia).³ We used the money we were paid to buy material that community members used to make a new meeting tent. We held a big FFLM that year [1978] to celebrate the new tent, which we kept for about forty years. We changed it [made a new tent] and celebrated a grand FFLM this year [2018]. A lags rgya mtsho [a local *bla ma*] was invited and gave teachings on the second day of FFLM.

In the past, all locals came for *yar tshogs thug pa* and *thor thug* when the managers shouted. All the ritual practitioners above sixteen-years-old were *thun*. Nobody practiced *sdom pa* on the second day of FFLM.

People often teased each other seriously, but no one got angry. Strangers were afraid to go near a place holding FFLM. Managers or other locals would catch the men and force them to overeat, locally known as *tsa rdzi* 'be hospitable'. Those skilled at *brtag re*⁴ and other talkative people were forced to drink liquid ghee if they resisted doing what was demanded. They might also have been teased by pouring yogurt or ghee on their heads. Such amusements are absent today. If we treat strangers or men from other communities like this, they might get angry.

¹ This ritual is held annually from the first to the seventh days of the eighth month near Grong brdal thog with monks from Dar zhing Monastery. The ritual is managed by men from the different local communities who take turns managing the ritual. At around three PM each day, participants sit around the meeting tent. Men and boys remove their shirts, or roll up their shirts to their neck. Girls and women roll up their shirts, exposing their backs. All place their palms together, touch their foreheads, and bend forward toward their knees. Monks walk in a line where participants sit in whatever order they like. The monks hold wooden bowls with water, sip water from the bowls, and spray it on the bare backs of participants who now kneel in a circle around the meeting tent. Two or three monks hold teapots with water to add when water in the bowls is finished. There is no debating, only chanting. See <https://bit.ly/2ImywSp> (accessed 4 October 2019) and <https://bit.ly/2lETOC6> (accessed 4 October 2019) for relevant video.

² He was imprisoned from 1958 to 1963.

³ A township in Rma chen (Maqin) County, Mgo log (Guoluo) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon Province.

⁴ *Btags sa* and *brtag re* denote teasing. *Brtag re* was popular among locals in 2019. *Btags sa* was less popular. *Btags sa* discloses secrets/hidden weaknesses. *Brtag re* occurs when two people or a group of people gather and tease each other face to face. The main purpose is to amuse the onlookers. I give examples related to *btags sa* of locals teasing each other during Smyung gnas.

FIG 15. Chos thog in 2019. Monks from Dar zhing Monastery chant and spray water from their mouths on people. This is locally known as *sngags gral* (7 September 2019, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Account Two: Gcod le and Tshe bkra

Once a year, Yo lag held FFLM at Bre ka'i thang. 'Gro skor held their FFLM at Khug rgan mdo. Two 'Gro skor villagers visited the Yo lag FFLM, and the managers treated them very hospitably. Later, one of them went some distance from the Yo lag FFLM, thinking he could elude the Yo lag villagers if they tried to catch him, and shouted, "*Ma mo yod no'i rig ga, mar khus shag wa yed ki, ma mo med no'i rig ga, ma rig kha bo bca' gi*." [You] offered a lot of ghee to those who have a lot of female sheep, [you] pretended not to see those with no sheep!"¹

Yo lag villagers chased that man on a hill between the 'Gro skor FFLM and the Yo lag FFLM. Both sides then came and wrestled for a long time. Some people were forcibly taken to an FFLM and made to overeat. Nobody was angry, even if they were uncomfortable.

Another incident occurred during the FFLM of Mkha' skya [Yo lag's neighbor] about forty years ago. A person nicknamed Bshur rkyal 'Boaster' visited the FFLM of that community. The Mkha' skya managers were hospitable. However, some elders advised the managers not to insist he overeat or he would be ill. This advice was accepted, and they released him.

That man went some distance, turned back on his horse, and shouted, "You guys didn't offer me any food today! I'm hungry, and now I'm eating my cold *rtsam pa*!" and pretended to eat a solid bit of *rtsam pa* from his robe pouch.

Some managers started chasing him, but some clever men shouted, "No, let him go!"

¹ Meaning: "You people are not very hospitable. You are only hospitable to my rich friend and ignore poor people like me." Locals greatly value hospitality, consequently, this man questioned their values to irritate them.

The man believed this and slowly continued on his way. After he went behind a hill, several Mkha' skya members secretly rode after him. The man suddenly kicked his horse with the stirrups when he realized he was being chased. His saddle's crupper broke, he fell off his horse, was brought back to his pursuers' FFLM, forced to overeat, and was mercilessly teased. He was made to drink bowls of ghee and eat *rtsam pa*. When he stopped eating, ghee and yogurt were poured on his head. This sort of teasing was typical during FFLM, and this man didn't get angry.

Account Three: Khon thar

When I (b. 1970) was twelve years old, we held FFLM in two adjoining brigades. We didn't have a meeting tent. Managers were not divided like today. All the villagers were managers. One summer [1978], some elders made a new meeting tent, which was the old one we put up last year [2017] for FFLM. [In 1978] we divided the managers into two groups like today. Those two groups have been taking turns holding Smyung gnas since that time. Today, we still follow these rules.

CONCLUSION

The Sa ga zla ba smyung gnas gathering described in this paper strengthens a sense of community among locals as they collectively eat, work, worship, and engage in recreational activities over three days.¹ In 1997, children played 'ba'² in groups of girls and boys. I knew all those children, though some were not my neighbors. This is an example illustrating how a strong sense of community membership was inculcated.

In 2019, many children attended school and had never experienced Smyung gnas. Furthermore, some children may not be acquainted unless they are from the same local community. Caterpillar fungus collecting is another reason some locals do not participate in Smyung gnas. It would be very positive if local primary school students were allowed to join in Smyung gnas in recognition of the value of traditional cultural activities that are rapidly changing.

Finally, I encourage locals throughout the Tibetosphere to consider giving careful, detailed attention to such rituals/gatherings as they are held locally, including reflections from local elders about how these activities have changed since their youth and what they think about these changes.

REFERENCES

Berzin, Alexander. 1987. An Introduction to Tibetan Astronomy and Astrology. *The Tibet Journal* 12(1):17-28. www.jstor.org/stable/43300228

Blo bzang bstan dar ལྷོ་བཟང་བསྟན་དར། 1994. *Dge slong ma dpal mo'i mdzad mam shel dkar phreng ba དགེ་སློང་མ་དཔལ་མའི་མཛད་རྟམ་ཤེལ་དཀར་ཤེང་བ།* [The Crystal Rosary Hagiography of Dge slong ma dpal mo]. TBRC W1KG14797. Delhi: Blo bzang bstan dar. <https://bit.ly/2Jwlpou>, accessed 8 July 2019

¹ The recreational activities following the *smyung gnas* proper occur because of the significance of the fourth month, as mentioned earlier. Such recreational activities do not occur following *smyung gnas* held in other months.

² See a description of this game at <https://at.virginia.edu/2XBuFFE> (accessed 8 July 2019), which involves choosing a certain number of stones and tossing up and catching an agreed upon number of stones while simultaneously arranging the other stones.

- Cabezón, José Ignacio. 2010. Introduction in José Ignacio Cabezón (ed) *Tibetan Ritual*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1-34.
- Caibu Dan 才布丹 [Tshe brtan ཚེ་བརྟན།]. 1993. Labuleng zangzu chuantong "niangnai jie" 拉卜楞藏族传统的"娘乃节" [Bla brang Tibetan Traditional Festival "Smyung gnas"]. *Fayin yuekan* 法音月刊 [Fayin Journal] 105:30-31.
- Dkon mchog bstan pa'i sgron me དཀོན་མཚོ་གཟུགས་པའི་སྒྲོན་མེ། nd [2003]. Smyung gnas kyi cho ga'i zur rgyan bde ba can gyi lam yig ces bya ba bzhugs so ལྷུང་གནས་ཀྱི་ཚོ་གཤི་ལུང་རྒྱན་བདེ་བ་ཅན་གྱི་ལམ་ཡིག་ཅེས་བྱ་བ་བཞུགས་སོ། [The Side-Ornament of Smyung gnas Guiding to the Blissful Realm] in *Dkon mchog bstan pa'i sgron me'i gsung 'bum ta དཀོན་མཚོ་གཟུགས་པའི་སྒྲོན་མེའི་གསུང་འབུམ།* ༩ [Collected Works of Dkon mchog bstan pa'i sgron me/ Vol 9]. TBRC W2DB4591. 11 vols. Pe cing བེ་ཅིང།: Mi rigs dpe skrun khang མི་རིགས་དཔེ་སླུང་ཁང། [Nationalities Publishing House], 160-189.
<https://bit.ly/2S1cJD8>, accessed 9 July 2019
- Gonier, Devin and Rgyal yum sgröl ma. 2012. Pyramid Schemes on the Tibetan Plateau. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 21:113-140. <https://bit.ly/2Jmpfer>, accessed 4 July 2019
- Nian Zhihai 年治海 and Bai Gengdeng 白更登 (eds). 1993. *Qinghai zangchuan fojiao siyuan mingjian* 青海藏传佛教寺院明鉴 [The Clear Mirror of Tibetan Buddhist Monasteries in Qinghai]. Lanzhou 兰州: Gansu minzu chubanshe 甘肃民族出版社 [Gansu Nationalities Press].
- Sang rgyas skyabs སངས་རྒྱས་སྐུབས། (Sangjijie 桑吉杰). 2018. *Mdo smad bsang khog gi smyung gnas dus chen dang de'i dngos yod rin thang la dpyad pa མདོ་སྐྱད་བསང་ལོག་གི་སྐྱུང་གནས་དུས་ཚིག་དང་དེའི་དངོས་ཡིད་རིན་པོ་ལ་དབྱེད་པ།* (Lun anduo sangke diqu "niangnai jie" jiqi xianshi yiyi 论安多桑科地区"娘乃节"及其现实意义) [On the Smyung gnas and Its Practical Meaning in Mdo smad Bsang khog]. Mtsho sngon mi rigs slob chen མཚོ་སྐྱོན་མི་རིགས་སློབ་ཆེན། Qinghai minzu daxue 青海民族大学 [Qinghai Nationalities University], MA thesis.
- Sangseraima Ujeed. 2016. Dge-slong-ma dpal-mo, the Princess, the Mahasiddha, the Nun and the Lineage Holder: as Presented in the *thob yig* of Za-ya Paṇḍita Blo-bzang 'phrin-las (1642-1715). *Journal of the Oxford Centre for Buddhist Studies* 5:128-166.
- Sonam Doomtso (Bsod nams dung mtsho བསོད་ནམས་དུང་མཚོ། Suolang Dongcuo 索朗东措). 2011. A Tibetan Nomad Girl's Changing Worlds. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 19.
<https://bit.ly/32tiQFk>, accessed 10 July 2019
- Vargas-O'bryan, Ivette M. 2001. The Life of Dge slong ma dpal mo: The Experiences of a Leper, Founder of a Fasting Ritual and Transmitter of Buddhist Teachings on Suffering and Renunciation in Tibetan Religious History. *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies* 24:157-185.
- Yang Xianhui 杨显惠. 2009. Niangnai Jie 娘乃节 [The Smyung gnas Festival]. *Shanghai wenxue* 上海文学 [Shanghai Literature] 2009(3):65-69.

Yu Shiyu 于式玉. 1941 [2002]. Niangnai 娘乃 in *Li Anzhai, Yu Shiyu zangxue wenlun xuan* 李安宅、于式玉藏学文论选 [Niangnai in *Collected Tibetology Papers of Li Anzhai & Yu Shiyu*]. Beijing 北京: Zhongguo zangxue chubanshe 中国藏学出版社 [China Tibetology Publishing House], 359-362.

Zhoumao Ta 周毛塔 ['Brug mo thar འབྲུག་མོ་ཐར་]. 2014. Labuleng minsu zhi "niangnai jie" 拉卜楞民俗之"娘乃节" [Smyung gnas: A Folk Custom of the Bla brang Area]. *Xizang yishu yanjiu* 西藏艺术研究 [*Tibetan Art Studies*] 2014(4):71-76.

TIBETAN TERMS

'ba' འབལ།	btsags thag chod pa བཅོགས་ཐག་ཚོད་པ།
'ba' rde'u འབལ་རེ་ལུ།	bzhi ba'i smyung gnas བཞི་བའི་སྐྱུང་གནས།
'bras thug འབྲས་ཐུག།	bzung 'dus mtsho བཟུང་འདུས་མཚོ།
'brug dkar tshe ring འབྲུག་དཀར་ཚེ་རིང་།	chab ཚབ།
'gro skor འགོ་སྐོར།	changs bu ཚངས་བུ།
'gyogs rdo འགྲོགས་རྩོ།	chos kho ཚོས་ཁོ།
'ja' mo འཇའ་མོ།	chos thog ཚོས་ཐོག།
'ju res འཇུ་རེས།	chu khog ཚུ་ཁོག།
'phyor l+wa འཕྱོར་ལ།	dar zhing དར་ཞིང་།
a mchog ཨ་མཚོག།	dge lugs དགོ་ལུགས།
bla brang ལྷ་བྲང་།	dge slong ma dpal mo དགོ་སྲོང་མ་དཔལ་མོ།
bla brang ma ལྷ་བྲང་མ།	dkar cog དཀར་ཚོག།
bla ma ལྷ་མ།	dkar mdzes དཀར་མཛེས།
blon che ལྷོན་ཚེ།	dmar དམར།
bon po བོན་པོ།	dpon skor དཔོན་སྐོར།
bre ka'i thang བྲེ་ཀའི་ཐང་།	g.yang mo གཡང་མོ།
brkyangs phyag བརྟུངས་ཕྱག།	g.yug res གཡུག་རེས།
brtag res བརྟག་རེས།	gcod le གཙོད་ལེ།
bsang chu བསང་ཚུ།	gcog གཙོག།
bsang khog བསང་ཁོག།	gro ma གྲོ་མ།
bshur rkyal བཤུར་རྒྱལ།	gtsang ma གཙང་མ།
bskums phyag བསྐུམས་ཕྱག།	gtsod གཙོད།
btags sa བཏགས་ས།	gung tshigs གུང་ཚིགས།

ja ras ཇ་རས།
ka chu ཀ་ཅུ།
ka ra ཀ་ར།
ka ra rdo ཀ་ར་རོ།
ka thog nas 'khor ཀ་ཐོག་ནས་འཛོལ།
kan lho ཀན་ལྷོ།
kan su'u ཀན་སུ་ཡུ།
khon thar ཁོན་ཐར།
khug rgan mdo ཁུག་རྒྱུ་མདོ།
khyed tshang la smyung gnas ba du yod ཁྱེད་མང་
ལ་སྐྱུང་གནས་བ་དུ་ཡོད།
khyi lnga ཁྱི་ལ།
ki thor thug 'thung gi shog ཀེ། ཐོར་ཐུག་འབྲུང་གི་ཤོག
ki yar tshogs thug pa 'thung gi shog ཀེ་ཡར་ཚོགས་
ཐུག་པ་འབྲུང་གི་ཤོག
lcags mo 'tsho ལཱ་གསལ་མོ་འཚོ།
ldong nge ལྷོང་ངེ།
lha mo skyabs ལྷ་མོ་སྐྱབས།
ling ལིང།
lus kyi sgrib pa ལུས་ཀྱི་སྐྱིབ་པ།
ma mo yod no'i rig ga/mar khus shag wa yed
ki/ma mo med no'i rig ga/ma rig kha bo bca'
gi མཚོ་ཡོད་ཚོའི་རིག་གཞི་མར་ལུས་ཤག་ལེད་ཀེ། མཚོ་མེད་ཚོའི་
རིག་གཞི་མ་རིག་ཁ་བོ་བཅའ་གི།
mar khu མར་ཁུ།
mchod khri མཚོད་ཁྱི།
mdo ba མདོ་བ།
mdo sngags dar rgyas gling མདོ་སྐྱབས་དར་རྒྱས་གླིང།
mdzod ras མཚོད་རས།
mgo log མགོ་ལོག།
mkha' skya མཁའ་སྐྱུ།
mtha' ba མཐའ་བ།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྐྱོན།
ngag gi sgrib pa ངག་གི་སྐྱིབ་པ།
ong ba ཨོང་བ།
pad+ma rig 'dzin པད་མ་རིག་འཛིན།
phrug l+wa ཕུག་ལ།
ra rgan ར་རྒྱུ།
ra rgya ར་རྒྱ།
ras gur རས་གུར།
ras gur dkar mdong རས་གུར་དཀར་མདོད།
ras gur klad nag རས་གུར་ལྷན་ནག།
ras l+wa རས་ལ།
reb gong རེབ་གོང།
rgya ma khyi tshang རྒྱ་མ་ཁྱི་མང།
rgya zhwa རྒྱ་ཞལ།
rin kho རིན་ཁོ།
rma chen རྩ་ཚེ།
rma lho རྩ་ལྷོ།
rnam lo རྩམ་ལོ།
rtsam pa རུམ་པ།
rtsam pa sgor log/gro log རུམ་པ་སྐོར་ལོག་གོ་ལོག།
ru khag རུ་ཁག།
rung ja རུང་ཇ།
rus cha རུས་ཇ།
sa ga zla ba ས་ག་ལྷ་བ།
sa ga zla ba'i dus chen ས་ག་ལྷ་བའི་དུས་ཚེ།
sa sgye ས་སྐྱེ།
sa skal ས་སྐལ།
sbyin bdag སྐྱིན་བདག།
sdom ja སྐོམ་ཇ།
sdom pa སྐོམ་པ།
sdom pa ba སྐོམ་པ་བ།
sgro b+ha སྐོར་བ།

sha bo don grub ཤ་བོ་དོན་གུབ།
 si khron སི་ཁྲོན།
 ska rags སྐ་རགས།
 smyung gnas སྐྱུང་གནས།
 smyung gnas ba སྐྱུང་གནས་བ།
 smyung gnas e bde thal སྐྱུང་གནས་ཨེ་བདེ་ཐལ།
 sngags gral སྐྱགས་གྲལ།
 stong skor ston mo སྟོང་སྟོར་སྟོན་མོ།
 su ru སུ་རུ།
 thag 'then ཐག་འཐེན།
 thor thug ཐོར་ཐུག།
 thugs rje chen po'i sbyin bsreg ཐུགས་རྗེ་ཆེན་པོའི་སྤྱིན་བསྐྱེད།
 thun ཐུན།
 tos ཐོས།
 tos bdun pa ཐོས་བདུན་པ།
 tos bzhi ba ཐོས་བཞི་བ།
 tos dang po ཐོས་དང་པོ།

CHINESE TERMS

Amuquhu 阿木去乎
 Chongqing 重庆
 dui 队
 Duowa 多哇
 Erdui 二队
 Gannan 甘南
 Gansu 甘肃
 Ganzi 甘孜
 Guangdong 广东
 Guangzhou 广州
 Guoluo 果洛
 Huangnan 黄南
 Kashijia 喀什加
 Lajia 拉加
 Linxia 临夏
 Liudui 六队
 Longwu 隆务
 Ma Bufang 马步芳

tos drug pa ཐོས་ལྷུག་པ།
 tos gnyis ba ཐོས་གཉིས་བ།
 tos gsum pa ཐོས་གསུམ་པ།
 tos lnga ba ཐོས་ལྔ་བ།
 tsa rdzi ཐ་རྗེ།
 tsag tsag ཐག་ཐག།
 tsha langs ba ཐ་ལངས་བ།
 tshe 'phags ཐེ་འཕགས།
 tshe bkra ཐེ་བཀྲ།
 tshe brtan ཐེ་བརྟན།
 tshe ring lo brgya ཐེ་རིང་ལོ་བརྒྱ།
 tshogs ras ཐོགས་རས།
 tshul khirms bstan 'dzin ཐུལ་ཁྲིམས་བསྟན་འཛིན།
 wu ba ཐུ་བ།
 yar tshogs thug pa ཡར་ཐོགས་ཐུག་པ།
 yid 'ong bzang mo ཡིད་འོང་བཟང་མོ།
 yid kyi sgrib pa ཡིད་ཀྱི་སྒྲིབ་པ།
 yo lag ཡོ་ལག།

Ma Qi 马麒
 Maqin 玛沁
 Meili xiangcun jianshe 美丽乡村建设
 Qidui 七队
 Qinghai 青海
 Qukuhu 曲库乎
 Sandui 三队
 Sangke 桑科
 Sichuan 四川
 Sidui 四队
 Tongren 同仁
 Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增
 Wudui 五队
 Xiahe 夏河
 Yidi fupin banqian 易地扶贫变迁
 Yidui 一队
 Zhiyue 直跃